

Women's Attainment of Self-Conservation from the Societal Clenches in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's Novel Sister of My Heart

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Shiyamala, B.

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B.Shiyamala

*Ph.D. Scholar, Periyar University College of Arts & Science
Mettur*

Abstract

The position of women in our society lacks the primordial aspect and dictated under the norms of subordination and ignorance. Men are bestowed to the aristocracy and succumb to accept women's interactional ability as they fear of what they might have to lose. Yet the society is unable to observe the fortunes they may receive in the future by allowing women to take equal opportunities. If the society wants to evolve and achieve greater goals, women who occupy half of the humanity should be acknowledged. Thus women are suffering from superiority issues, traditional roles and inadequacy of understanding among themselves. Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni explains the need of autonomy and their rights of selecting their own happiness in her novel Sister of my Heart. Chitra Banerjee published this novel in 1999, which presents the emancipation of two women from their boundaries through their own flow and ebb. It narrates the journey of Anju and Sudha, who have been raised in a matriarchal household and left to the patriarchal society after their marriage. As a result, their deep bonding helps them to prevent stumbling from the disasters and support each other at the verge of falling apart. The author makes the protagonists to realise their needs and evolve them out of their stagnation.

In her book, *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*, Mary Wollstonecraft says, “let them not be treated like slaves; or, like the brutes who are dependent on the reason of man, when they associate with him; but cultivate their minds, give them the salutary, sublime curb of principle, and let them attain consciousness dignity by feeling themselves only dependent in God” (48). Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's second novel *Sister of my Heart* penetrates Solacement with evident to reciprocal bonding of sisterhood. The author tried to unearth the longing of women to enhance their role as an individual and not as a doldrums. Chitra Banerjee makes her protagonists Anjali and Basudha to dream a world beyond suppression and verdicts by making them as a new woman, who survives as a rebel rather than a victim in the hands detestable tradition and patriarchy. The novel revolves around the two sisters who were born on the same day and meticulously possess different natures and aspirations towards their life. But their love for each other mends all difference of opinions and shoulder each other's burden and errors. Anju states that, “I could never hate Sudha. Because she is my other half. The sister of my heart” (*Sister of My Heart* 11).

The Chatterjee house is managed by three widowed women yet it is bounded by the patriarchal rules. Gouri and Pishi who are Anju's mother and aunt always seek the empowerment of the girls and insist them to get good education. Even after the death of both men Gopal (a distant relative and Nalini's husband) and Bijoy (Gouri's husband) in a ruby hunting, Gouri Ma determined to take care of the household and to bring them up to the standards of Chatterjee girls. But Nalini, (Sudha's mother) is huddled in the belief of typical Indian woman, whose prime duty is to guide and take care of her husband and proposes a woman's highest respect will be earned through marriage. Anju is the one who struggles and questions the inclined society's nature and limitations harboured by a woman whereas Sudha possess a calm nature to flow with the events. Their dreams of future are evident to observe their nature. When Anju expresses her dream as, "I want to run the bookstore. It'll be hard to persuade Mother but I'm sure I can. After all I'm her only child, with no competing brothers. That's why I'm planning to study literature in college" (SMH 74), Sudha wants to have a happy married life and a family.

According to Kate Millet, "Patriarchal ideology exaggerates biological differences between men and women, making certain that men always have the dominant or masculine roles and that women always have the subordinate or feminine ones" (Feminism: A Paradigm Shift, 159). The author represents the prevailing case of women through Pishi, who had been secluded from everything due her widowhood. She says, "But when after three years of being a widow I begged my father to get me a private tutor so I'd at least have my studies to occupy me, he slapped me across the face. I considered suicide, oh yes, many times in those early years" (SMH 248). Anju boldly opposes this suppression and states this has been resulted from keeping them as 'prize cows' (SMH 52).

However, the author exemplifies how the women are preserving each other from all the clutches of society to obtain happiness and individuality. Once Sudha and Anju have visited the theatre secretly and happened to meet Ashok. Sudha's vibrant attitude is exposed after meeting Ashok, a smart and lovely boy at the theatre and falls in love with him. As it is reported by Sarita aunty, who caught them red-handed, Sudha has been punished by her mother by putting a halt to her education. For Nalini, acceptance of society and its opinion is very important than her daughter's concern. Though, Anju is blessed with an understanding mother, her dream of higher education is shattered by the worst health condition of Gouri Ma. Both the girls have been prepared for marriage. Anju says, "Remember how I promised you, the night your mother decided to shut you up at home, that I'd make sure the same things would happen to us both? Well, they have" (SMH 91). It provokes Sudha to make a plan of elopement with Ashok at the same time their alliances have been set up.

But when Sudha realises the hardness and expectations of Manjumdar, the future in-laws of Anju, she puts off her elopement plan for the sake of Anju. Since, Anju falls for Sunil; Sudha sacrifices her desire and love. She wants to preserve the happiness of Anju and from falling into a shame due to her elopement. Sudha explains, "When we reach the garden, the sun is a parched emptiness in the sky because Sunil's father will never let him marry a girl whose cousin eloped with a man she met in a movie house" (SMH 124). So she accepts to marry Ramesh, according to the wish of elders. As planned, their marriage had taken place and the dear sisters met their separation for the first time. Anju settles happily in America, her dream land with her loving husband Sunil and Sudha gets adapted with the Sanyal family at Bardhaman. As days passed, Sudha is criticised and pressured by her mother-in-law for not conceiving a baby. The author expresses the maltreatment of society on women if they fail to bear a child. Raged with Sudha's despair Anju exasperatedly says to Sunil, "You probably don't even see anything wrong in treating a woman that way. You probably agree with all those Indian men who see a woman as nothing more than a baby machine" (SMH 193). In order to avoid criticism, woman has to silently bear all the humiliations.

Even though Sudha gets pregnant, her mother-in-law forces her to abort the womb after knowing that Sudha is conceived with a girl child. In many part of India, people always expect a son to born first. This apparently shows how even the right of woman on her womb has been denied and dictated by someone else. In her book *A Room of One's Own*, Virginia Woolf states, "For if two sexes are quite inadequate, considering the vastness and variety of the world, how should we manage with one only? Ought not education to bring out and fortify the differences rather than the similarities?" (79). When Ramesh fails to protect his wife and daughter, Anju advises Sudha to leave the house and Sudha in order to preserve her daughter's life and her responsibilities as a mother breaks the boundaries of a typical Indian woman. She precisely chooses to be a good mother instead of being a wife to a man, who flunks to protect them. As Sudha expresses, "When the test showed that it was a girl, my mother-in-law said the eldest child of the Sanyal family has to be male- that's how it's been in the last five generations. She said it's not fitting, it'll bring the family shame and ill luck" (SMH 238).

Though the mothers of the house at first gets surprised and tries to console the Sanyals, later they start to preserve the life of both Sudha and her daughter Dayita. They try everything to comfort Sudha and support her choices. They stand as an example for providing solace to their lovable daughter when she needs them the most. But it is not the case with every abandoned woman due to dowry issues, infertility and men's flaws. The author gives the resolution as well as enhances the support of womanhood. Adding to this, Anju wants to provoke the other possibilities for a fresh start at America. When Sunil doesn't show any interest in Sudha's affairs, Anju decides to preserve her cousin's self-respect and prop her up with new opportunities, which cannot be yielded in India as she breaks the boundaries. Anju says, "I will bring Sudha and her daughter to America. Why not! She can sew clothes for all the Indian ladies here and maybe finally-open the boutique she dreamed of" (SMH 254). In her striving for Sudha, Anju's health has been deteriorated and resulted in Anju's miscarriage.

At that time, Ashok shows his willingness to accept Sudha and she is extremely happy to have her love back. But again, she wants to preserve her beloved Anju's health and mental happiness instead of her love. And Sudha realises the need of self-sufficiency and to create a new environment where her Dayita will be free from the classification and doubtful notions of society. As a mother she needs to provide a peaceful and lively surrounding where Dayita can dream more than her mother. Sudha sorely needs a change from the clutches of society which is ready to stamp each woman for their flaws and inadequacy. Finally the sisters reunited at America with new hopes and Solacement. Anju expresses her joy as, "But for now the three of us stand unhurried, feeling the way we fit, skin on skin, into each other's live. A rain- dampened sun struggles from the clouds to frame us in its hesitant, holy light" (SMH 322).

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